

Method to Calculate the Total Cost of Ownership of Infrastructure as a Service

Marion Devouassoux
IT department
CERN

16 October 2018

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Abstract

This document provides a method to calculate the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) of infrastructure level cloud services (IaaS). It focuses on the storage, compute and networking requirements of WLCG workloads. A comparison of colocation data centre and commercial cloud provider provisioning as a means of extending the capacity available in the CERN Meyrin data centre is included.

Acknowledgement

I would like to thank the following CERN IT people for their valuable inputs to this study:

- Alberto Pace, Storage Group Leader
- Bob Jones, External Funded Projects Section Leader
- Christian Isnard, Departmental Planning Officer (DPO)
- David Foster, Data Protection Officer
- Edoardo Martelli, Communication Systems, Projects & Operations
- Eric Grancher, Databases Group Leader
- João Fernandes, External Funded Projects Technical Officer
- Miroslav Potocky, Database, Infrastructure, Management & Storage Services
- Tim Bell, Compute & Monitoring Group Leader
- Tony Cass, Communication Systems Group Leader
- Wayne Salter, Compute Management Group Leader

Introduction

The Helix Nebula Science Cloud project (www.HNSciCloud.eu) is building a European hybrid cloud platform to support the deployment of high-performance computing and big-data capabilities for scientific research. Cost effectiveness versus performance of the solution being a core aspect of the project, one objective is to assess and compare the cost of ownership of colocation and cloud-based solutions. This study contributes to the planning of the provision of extra capacity for LHC Run 3 as decided at the CERN IT department meeting Programme of Work (PoW) Preparation meeting held on 7 June 2018:

“It was decided that the plan to provide the extra capacity needed for Run3 is to cost potential external solutions for 2019-2023. These would be for physics computing only, focusing on keeping most storage at CERN; develop caching, latency-hiding, and similar techniques to optimize the delivery of data to remote compute.”

Measuring the full cost of a solution is complex: costs are often hidden, partially visible or unaccounted for. In addition, cost factors vary from a colocation to a cloud-based solution, making the cost comparison more difficult. Finally, not only the costs are important but also the qualitative aspects of the solutions.

To address these challenges, a method is proposed to calculate and compare the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) of provisioning IaaS that is adapted to the research environment. The

method considers cost categories identified when comparing colocation¹ and cloud-based² solutions. The development of this method was a four-step process that took several months:

1. A TCO framework was identified to serve as a base for the study. This framework³ was developed in April 2015 by an EDUCAUSE-ECAR working group composed of 20 experts in ICT working in universities and IT companies. The ECAR framework provides a holistic approach as it is composed of a risk assessment, a quantitative analysis and a qualitative evaluation. In each category, the colocation solution is directly compared to the cloud-based solution.
2. The framework was then adapted to suit the use-case of research infrastructures handling scientific data. Some cost factors were removed, some were modified and other were added.
3. The customized framework was then used to calculate the TCO of CERN's usage of the rented Wigner DC⁴ hosting facility as the basis for the colocation example. The figures for this study were provided by personnel in CERN-IT.
4. Information gathering interviews with CERN-IT personnel involved in the DC daily operations. The method and the results for the Wigner DC were presented. The feedback collected during the interviews was used to improve the method.

The method described in this paper is the result of the process outlined above. It is important to note that each cost factor can be interpreted and assessed differently and this paper proposes one way of calculating both colocation and commercial cloud TCO intended to achieve consensus among the stakeholders consulted.

To effectively compare the Wigner DC and the commercial cloud TCO, one first needs to fully understand the role of the Wigner DC. Wigner DC is presented as an extension of the WLCG Tier 0⁵, a host for other IT services as well as a means of ensuring business continuity and disaster recovery. These roles overlap but not all of the associated functionality is required for WLCG workloads. These overlapping roles make it difficult to separate-out those costs associated with the WLCG workloads from those associated with business continuity and disaster recovery. Clarifying these points before comparing the Wigner DC to a commercial cloud solution is important because it will determine the quality of service and infrastructure requirements and hence overall costs as well as the importance given to the qualitative factors. The overlap of roles between Wigner DC and building 513 on the Meyrin site has also impacted this costing exercise because resources and services are split across the two sites. It has been possible to separate the majority of material costs but finding an acceptable means of separating manpower costs, especially concerning the operational aspect, is more difficult. In its current status, the study only includes manpower costs linked to the integration of a new DC and excludes operational manpower costs.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Colocation_centre

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Infrastructure_as_a_service

³ <https://library.educause.edu/~media/files/library/2015/4/ewg1503-pdf.pdf>
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/15jcWAGJnA55RsFOY5IjyRzz3EfdDLLESDPR_G3zPxsM/edit?usp=sharing

⁴ <http://information-technology.web.cern.ch/opendays2013/wigner>

⁵ <http://wlcg-public.web.cern.ch/tier-centres>

Therefore, it calculates the total cost of extending the initial capacity of the Meyrin DC with the Wigner DC rather than a TCO of the Wigner DC, and cannot be compared to commercial cloud TCO as such.

This paper follows the structure of the ECAR-framework: it starts with a high-level assessment of two foundational risks, continues with the financial analysis and finishes with a qualitative comparison of colocation and commercial cloud solutions.

1. Foundational risks

The foundational risks part consists of a high-level assessment of two risks: data sensitivity and business criticality. The method to assess the risks is the following: first each risk is given an importance (High / Medium / Low). Then the colocation and commercial cloud solutions are relatively assessed according to the following scoring method:

+1	Among the options studied, the solution that mitigates the risk studied in the most effective way scores +1.
0	Among the options studied, a solution that demonstrates capacity to mitigate the risk studied and is not the most effective solution to mitigate this risk scores 0.
-1	Among the options studied, a solution that shows little evidence of capacity to mitigate the risk studied scores -1.

Data sensitivity

Importance of the risk:

Scientific data from the LHC experiments are not confidential and already distributed among many data centres through the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG). Therefore, a disclosure of these data would be undesirable but not highly harmful to CERN. However, access to data from a specific LHC experiment needs to be restricted to members of the experiment. A breach in the access control would damage the relationship of trust between the experiment and CERN. Therefore, the importance of the data sensitivity in the research environment is considered Low.

Relative assessment of the two solutions (colocations and commercial cloud):

We are trying to understand which solution proposes the most appropriate security controls to maintain the confidentiality of the data being processed. One assessment method consists of looking at third party controls and certifications.

CERN is responsible for the cybersecurity and the protection of the data deployed in Wigner. CERN has no certification such as the ISO/IEC 27000-series on information

security standards and is preparing to become compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Concerning cloud providers based in Europe, most of them are certified ISO/IEC 27000 series and are obliged to comply with the GDPR as of May 2018, failing which they face heavy fines.⁶

However, one could argue that the lack of certifications does not necessarily reflect the quality of the service provided since the public research sector has no specific certification obligations.

To conclude, both solutions offer satisfying security controls and therefore score +1.

Business criticality

Importance of the risk:

A business critical function is a function without which an organisation cannot operate or remain viable. The storage and compute of the WLCG data is a business critical function of the organisation. A loss of this data would considerably harm the reputation of CERN. We note that this assessment concerns the WLCG data as a whole. If a subset of the data is lost, it can potentially be recovered thanks to the data replication across WLCG tier-1 centres. Wigner holds a copy of a subset of the WLCG data. Incidents to WLCG tier-1 centres, such as water damage at INFN in Bologna in 2017, indicate that data recovery, even if possible, is a labour intensive and time consuming task. Thus the importance is considered Medium.

Relative assessment of the two solutions (colocation and commercial cloud):

We are trying to understand if the options enable sufficient availability and integrity of the data. The availability and integrity of the data can be affected by the following aspects:

- The network availability:

The Wigner DC is connected to Meyrin through three network links each with a bandwidth of 100 Gbit/sec with redundant physical connections⁷. The network connection between the Wigner DC and the closest Point of Presence (PoP) in the GÉANT network has also a bandwidth of 100 Gbit/sec on two diverse paths.

Within the pilot phase of the HNSciCloud project, the cloud providers are required to provide a minimum bandwidth of 40 Gbit/sec through the GÉANT network either directly or via an NREN.⁸ If an external cloud service provider were to be used as an important production site for WLCG then it would require a dedicated network connection similar to that put in place for Wigner DC.

- The infrastructure availability:

The Service Level Agreement (SLA) between Wigner and CERN ensures a high level of service availability at the infrastructure level. For instance, a maximum number of abrupt interruptions of the equipment is low (once every two years for

⁶ <https://www.eugdpr.org/>

⁷ Interview with David Foster

⁸ Annex C of the request for tender of the HNSciCloud design phase

non-critical equipment and zero for critical equipment), the intervention times in case of problems are defined (less than 1 working day for on-critical systems and less than 4 working hours for critical systems) and the temperature of the room is controlled. Moreover, there is a high level of redundancy at the infrastructure level, i.e. most of the component have spares⁹, and all systems are equipped with UPS.

According to the various documents¹⁰ produced within the HNSciCloud project, storage unavailability, premature VM termination, network outage (including levels of packet loss exceeding 1%) and API unavailability may be sanctioned.

Based on the above paragraph, both solutions prove to provide satisfactory levels of data availability and integrity and thus score + 1.

Conclusions of the risk assessment

The importance ranking is treated as a weighting factor and applied to the relative assessment for each solution: high = 3, medium = 2, and low = 1

Foundational Risk	Importance of the risk	Wigner DC	Cloud-based solution
Data sensitivity	Low	+ 1	+ 1
Business criticality	Medium	+ 2	+ 2
Total		+ 3	+ 3

⁹ Interview with Balazs Bago, Deputy head of Wigner data center (12 February 2018)

¹⁰ Phases Work Orders, Cloud Services Agreements for Early Adopters, Phases Functional Specifications.

2. Quantitative factors

Quantitative factors are elements where the annual costs can readily be identified. These factors are grouped in three categories: Hidden Subsidies and Indirect Costs, One-time costs and Ongoing costs. For each cost factor listed below, the yearly cost over four years is calculated (to offset the effect of annual variations). This section explains the calculation method for the colocation solution only. The results can then be compared to the figures delivered directly by the cloud providers. The assumption of a fixed currency exchange rate is made.

Hidden Subsidies and Indirect Costs

Hidden Subsidies and Indirect Costs are cost factors often unrecognized in cost studies.

Facility cost:

Facility cost correspond to the cost of hosting the servers in the data centre. The overall capacity procured and installed at Wigner is 3500 servers, 29 700 disks (equivalent to 94PB of raw storage). The hosting fee for this capacity is calculated as follows:

Hosting Fee = monthly floor space cost + monthly purchase cost of racks to host equipment

Where Monthly floor space cost = daily cost of floor space per rack * number of installed racks * number of operating days of the racks during the month

And Monthly purchase cost of racks = total cost of buying one rack * number of racks installed within the first 36 months (according to the profile in the Service level agreement) / 36 months.

It was agreed in the contract that CERN will only pay the racks bought within the first 36 months of the contract. After this date, only the floor space cost is billed. The racks continue to be operational for a longer period. Consequently, the cost of the racks is depreciated over the validity of the contract in this study.

Electricity and Energy costs for running the infrastructure.

This corresponds to the cost of the electricity required to run the infrastructure providing the service, including cooling. The Wigner data centre has a capacity of 2.5MW¹¹. The monthly electricity cost is based on the actual consumption and is calculated as follows:

Monthly electricity cost = cost per kWh (fixed cost) * monthly consumption in kWh * Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE).

For the Wigner DC, the electricity cost calculation is based on an estimated PUE¹² of 1.5.

Network cost:

Three optical fibre links are connecting the Wigner DC to the Meyrin DC. The network costs for these links are accounted as followed:

¹¹ Source:

<https://home.cern/about/updates/2013/06/cern-inaugurates-data-centre-extension-budapest>

¹² This estimated PUE was given by Wigner in its response to the call for tender.

- Cost of the two optical fibre links (dedicated bandwidth: 100 Gbit/sec each) operated by GÉANT. These links go from the GÉANT PoP located in the Meyrin DC and the GÉANT PoP in Hungary.
- Cost of the two diverse path of 100 Gbit/sec each between the GÉANT PoP in Hungary and the Wigner DC. No network cost is billed for the connexion between Meyrin and the GÉANT network as there is a GÉANT PoP directly in the Meyrin DC.
- Cost of one optical fibre link (dedicated bandwidth: 100 Gbit/sec) operated by T-Systems. This link directly connects the Meyrin DC to the Wigner DC.

None of these links have internet connectivity, nor network peering.

Note: this cost factor does not include the internal network infrastructure costs. They are counted as a one-time cost.

Insurance cost:

The monthly insurance is calculated using the following formula:

Monthly insurance cost = value of the installed equipment * number of months in one year / fixed multiplier value.

Disaster Recovery System and Business continuity and recovery:

The Disaster Recovery System is the operational cost to ensure the service can continue to be available and/or can be restored to operation in the event of a disaster. This includes tape backups, redundant storage facilities, failover computing facilities and potentially maintaining an off-site co-location facility. Business continuity and recovery is the cost associated with the response to a disaster incident and restoring the service to operation.

As mentioned earlier, the tier level of the Wigner DC and its role in business continuity for the WLCG data remain unclear. These cost factors cannot be measured provided this question remains outstanding.

One-time costs

One-time costs are cost factors that arise during the implementation phase of the solution.

Hardware acquisition costs

The typical server deployed at Wigner is a 2U quad system with the following:

- 32x virtual cores spread over two CPUs
- 64GB of RAM
- 2x 1TB SSD (last delivery) or 2x 2TB HDD (first deliveries) for the operating system
- 1x 10GbE network interface for data
- 1x dedicated management network interface

The team IT-CF-FPP is in charge of procuring the hardware. Since the beginning of the contract with Wigner, hardware has been procured on three separate occasions: 2013, 2014 and 2016. The method to calculate the yearly hardware acquisition cost is the following:

Hardware cost = Sum of the purchasing costs of the hardware (in 2013, 2014 and 2016) / length of the contract with Wigner in years.

This cost includes a three years warranty on the material and the transport to Budapest. It excludes the cost of installing the equipment (listed thereafter). The hardware maintenance cost is counted as an ongoing cost (listed below).

Internal networking infrastructure acquisition costs:

This cost factor includes the acquisition and shipping costs of the switches, routers, router modules, transceivers, cables and firewalls which are purchased by the group IT-CS.

At Wigner, the following ratios apply: 1 switch connects 40 servers and 1 router connects 150 switches.

It is necessary to include the purchasing costs of the following items:

- The routers modules and transceivers used in Meyrin to connect the three networking links between Budapest and Meyrin. There are procured by the group IT-CS.
- The Optical fibres and UTP Ethernet patches used in the Wigner DC to connect switches and servers. This equipment is procured directly by the Wigner DC.

The internal network maintenance cost is counted as ongoing costs (listed below).

Note: the transportation costs for back and forth shipments of defective materials between Meyrin and Budapest are not counted.

Equipment installation costs:

The monthly installation fee for the hardware is calculated as follows:

Installation fee = Cost of installing one rack * Number of newly installed racks in the month

This cost includes:

- The installation of the racks and the servers by the employees of the Wigner DC.
- The installation of internal network infrastructure by the employees of the Wigner DC.
- The installation cost of the network connection from the Wigner DC to the closest GÉANT PoP.

Note: this cost is both a one-time and ongoing cost as the racks have been installed regularly throughout the contract based on the SLA.

Software acquisition:

The same software are running in Wigner and in the Meyrin DC and no additional subscription fees are required to run them in two different locations.

There is a maintenance cost that is counted as a manpower cost listed below.

Integration costs:

Integrating a new DC into current systems and services requires specific actions:

- Customization of the tools at the new DC to meet existing business processes (or change existing business processes to be compatible with the additional DC)
- Redesigning the current services and systems to take optimal advantage of new DC
- Moving the data and the equipment to the new DC.

Manpower effort is required to implement these actions, which represents a cost for the organisation. The details of the manpower effort needed to integrate the Wigner DC is not available. The minimum required effort is estimated at 2 FTEs for 1.5 years.

The standard personnel cost¹³ of these FTEs (not the salary) must be taken into account, to integrate costs born by the organisation (pension, health insurance, etc.) Following the rule for H2020 EC projects, a 25% flat-rate of the total manpower cost is added to reflect overheads.

Ongoing costs

Ongoing costs are cost factors that continue during the operation of the service.

Equipment Maintenance cost (performed by Wigner DC under contract):

This encompasses all the support service performed by the Wigner technical staff both on hardware and internal networking infrastructure. It is a fixed amount calculated as follows:

Maintenance = Monthly cost of support service during working hours (as defined in Technical specifications + monthly cost of repairs according to profile in SLA).

The manpower effort from CERN for repairs on hardware and on internal networking infrastructure is counted in the manpower cost.

Equipment Maintenance costs (performed by external companies):

A fee is paid to an external company for replacement of broken parts and the resolution of software bugs on some of the internal networking infrastructure.

No maintenance fee is paid to external companies on the hardware. However the equipment has a warranty of three years, which is included in the purchasing price.

Software Licensing:

As the study focuses on the infrastructure level, and WLCG uses free Linux OS, no software licensing costs are considered.

Data Ingress and Egress costs:

¹³ The standard personnel costs at CERN table is available on the FAP website:
<https://fap-dep.web.cern.ch/ef/horizon-2020-projects-0>

In the case of the Wigner DC, this cost is included in the networking cost factor.

Conclusions of the quantitative analysis

The graph below shows the cost breakdown of the Wigner data centre following the method described above.

3. Qualitative costs

Qualitative factors are those that cannot easily be translated into financial terms but represent significant advantages or disadvantages of a solution that should be considered when comparing alternatives.

As for the risk assessment part, each factor is given an importance (High, Medium or Low). Then the colocation and commercial cloud solutions are relatively assessed according to the following scoring method:

+1	Among the options studied, the solution providing the best service quality for a given factor scores +1.
0	Among the options studied, a solution that demonstrates medium service quality for a given factor scores 0.
-1	Among the options studied, a solution that shows poor service quality for a given factor scores -1.

As cloud service offers vary greatly according to the provider, the type of agreement, the amount of resources committed etc. it is not possible to assess the Wigner DC against an abstract cloud provider. It must be compared directly against an actual offer from one cloud provider. Therefore, the following section presents only the assessment of the performance of the Wigner DC for each factor. The service quality will be rated either poor, medium or good. This assessment is summarized in a table and will be used to perform the relative assessment against a commercial cloud solutions based on an actual offer. As for the risk assessment, the importance ranking will then be treated as a weighting factor and applied to the relative assessment for each solution: high = 3, medium = 2, and low = 1.

Agility

Agility is the ability to customize the service provided to best fit the needs of the organisation.

Importance of the factor:

The agility of the service provided affects the overall efficiency. If the VMs are not an appropriate core to RAM ratio for the WLCG use cases then some resources may be wasted. Therefore, the importance of agility is considered Medium.

Assessment of the Wigner DC:

The VMs created on servers deployed in Wigner are managed using OpenStack. The customization is therefore done directly by the users. The Wigner DC provides a highly agile service.

Contract Review and Negotiation

This factor corresponds to the time and effort necessary to implement to the solution.

Importance of the factor:

On the one hand, the need for new capacity from the experiments is forecasted on a yearly basis. Thus, the contract negotiation can be anticipated. On the other hand, a long lasting relationship with a capacity provider is economically advantageous as it suppresses the need to run a new procurement cycle and reinstall regularly the equipment. The importance of this factor is considered Medium.

We understand that the contract with Wigner is a hosting contract (the servers remain the propriety of CERN and are managed under a separate contract). For a fair comparison, we consider a prepaid multi-year reserved instance contract or a prepaid multi-year bare metal contract with a cloud provider.

Assessment of the Wigner DC:

If a new contract for hosting capacity is negotiated, the CERN internal procurement guideline would apply. As the investment would probably be above 750,000 CHF, a departmental request, market survey followed by invitation to tender and the Finance Committee approval are required¹⁴. Wayne Salter estimated this process to take up to one year. Note that this guideline would also apply for the use of commercial cloud service.

Wigner and CERN have experience in doing business together. The two organisations can build on this experience to extend the current contract (ending in 2019). The contract maintenance with Wigner is facilitated by the fact that the fee charged is independent of the workload (i.e. number of VMs, amount of data stored and the data ingress and egress).

Elasticity and Scalability

Elasticity and Scalability are the ability to provide easy and quick expansion of available processing and/or storage capacity during times of peak need and reduction of that same capacity during times of lower need.

Importance of the factor:

While the experiments are asked to forecast their computing needs on a yearly basis, they may perform better (i.e. performance of the detector and accelerator chain) or worse than expected (i.e. due to technical problems). As a result, the importance of the factor is Low.

Assessment of the Wigner DC:

Tim Bell estimated that the public procurement cycle for hardware at CERN takes about 280+ days.¹⁵ Specifically for Wigner, Wayne Salter estimated procurement to take about 180

¹⁴ <https://procurement.web.cern.ch/en/procurement-guidelines-at-a-glance>

¹⁵ https://indico.cern.ch/event/624572/contributions/2521258/attachments/1460039/2256490/20170517_SKA_CERN_Computing_v2.pdf

days, and another 60 days are needed to get the hardware operational.¹⁶ As these delays are significant, the service quality is considered poor.

Regulatory and Policy Requirements

CERN, as an international organization, is exempted from external regulations. Therefore only the regulations concerning data privacy will be considered in this study, and more specifically the General Data Privacy Regulation (GDPR¹⁷).

Importance of the factor:

While the data privacy is of the utmost concern in general, only metadata are associated to the LCG data, i.e. IP addresses. Therefore the importance of the factors in the context of the study is considered Low.

Assessment of colocation solution:

Note that CERN remains the owner of the data processed in Wigner. Therefore the data privacy protection is analysed at the level of CERN. An Office for Data Privacy Protection (ODDP) was launched at CERN to make sure that best practices for handling personal data are adopted.

Note that the equipment deployed at Wigner is protected by CERN's diplomatic immunities and privileges. Therefore, no external investigation of the data can be done without the consent of the CERN Director General¹⁸. Pending formal adoption of CERN's policies for Data Privacy Protection, this factor is assessed as Fair.

Security

In this factor, the mechanisms to prevent constantly expanding security threats and to monitor for security events or breaches, both at a physical and cyber level are studied.

Importance of the factor:

The importance of the factor is High as security is a major concern at CERN.

Assessment of colocation solution:

- Physical security: the Wigner data centre is considered secure (armed guards, camera system, 24h/day surveillance, restrictive access control etc.)¹⁹
- Cyber-security: it is operated by the CERN Computer Security Office. There is no external certification on information security management.

¹⁶ Interview with Wayne Salter (09 February 2018)

¹⁷ Interview with David Foster (26 February 2018)

¹⁸ Interview with Wayne Salter (09 February 2018)

¹⁹ Interview with Balazs Bago, Deputy head of Wigner data center (12 February 2018)

CERN is the only customer of the Wigner DC. Commercial cloud service providers typically have more clients and offer efficient security tools to ensure isolation across clients in their multi-client environment.

Service levels

This factor analyzes the level of service expected from the service provider regarding the availability, the monitoring, and the support of the service.

Importance of the factor:

The availability of the service and the support associated is a basic requirement that both solutions have to fulfil. The importance of the service level is High.

Assessment of colocation solution:

The assessment thereafter is based on the SLA for the Provision of a Hosting Facility for the Wigner Data Centre (contract number IT-3836/IT/Hosting Service).

Service availability:

Type of equipment	Accepted Interruptions	Maximum intervention times
Non-Critical	Abrupt interruption: once every two years for less than 4 hours	1 working day
Critical	Abrupt interruption : none Power cut with 10 minutes of power supply to allow the servers to be shut down in a controlled manner: once every two years for less than 4 hours	4 working hours

Historically, there has been no failure on the hardware deployed by Wigner since the start of the contract in 2013. There has been one breach in the SLA due to the temperature rising above the limit. Wayne Salter estimated the service availability at Wigner to be above 99.0%. However there have been failures on the network and none of the three links is currently using the recently installed secondary networking hub at CERN. ²⁰

Support: a first line support is provided during working hours (8 working hours between the hours of 07:00 and 19:00 CET).

Monitoring:

Changes to the monitored values must be provided to the CERN monitoring system within the following maximum delays:

²⁰ Interview with Wayne Salter (09 February 2018)

Type of equipment	Maximum warning delays
Current power usage of CERN equipment	10 minutes
Current capacity of UPS systems (if used)	1 minute
Infrastructure alarms indicating faults potentially affecting CERN equipment, including any loss of redundancy	5 seconds
Relevant temperature and humidity readings for the cooling infrastructure, e.g. inlet and return temperature of cooling air (and/or water), humidity of inlet air	1 minute

To sum up, the Wigner DC offers a high service availability, a satisfactory monitoring service and quick response in case of incidents. The Wigner DC SLA only covers the hosting facility not the installed hardware which is subject to a separate contract between CERN and the supplier. CERN is responsible for the IaaS services deployed on the hardware and offered to users. For a comparison with commercial cloud services, the hosting facility, hardware and basic IaaS service would be covered by the same contract and SLA.

Conclusions of the qualitative assessment

Qualitative factor	Importance of the risk	Wigner DC
Agility	Medium	Good
Contract Review and Negotiation	Medium	Fair
Elasticity and Scalability	Medium	Poor
Regulatory and Policy Requirements	Low	Fair
Security	High	Good
Service levels	High	Good

Summary

The method to calculate the Total Cost of Ownership takes into account Foundational risks, Quantitative and Qualitative factors. These factors have been estimated for colocation solutions and partially for commercial cloud solutions based on input from HNSciCloud. In terms of risks, the solutions are assessed as being equal. The quantitative analysis is currently incomplete since it does not include manpower costs. To complete the analysis, CERN-IT personnel are asked to provide estimates of manpower effort dedicated to the integration and operation of the colocation solution (i.e. table “Manpower effort needed to integrate the Wigner DC” page 10 and “IT Staff involved in Data Centre Operations” p13). Major non-manpower costs include hardware, facility services and energy. In terms of qualitative factors, the colocation solution ensures a high availability of the service in an agile and safe environment. Data privacy protection and implementation time are considered satisfactory. The study does not take into account the performance of the solutions considered. Performance could be judged using benchmarking techniques, such as KVM²¹ for CPU and an equivalent for storage, and taken into account as a quantitative factor. The assumed utilisation level throughout the study is 100%. Any level inferior to this figure leads to an increase in the total cost per unit both for colocation and commercial cloud reserved instances.

Future Work

The costs for both colocation and commercial cloud solutions decrease regularly. Consequently, we propose to use the above method to calculate both colocation and commercial cloud TCO on a regular basis. The figures for the quantitative factors and the details for the qualitative factors for commercial cloud solutions will be delivered directly by the cloud providers. The first comparison will be made when the cloud providers involved in the HNSciCloud project will deliver a TCO study in September 2018.

The results have been reviewed at the CERN IT department Programme of Work events and used as input for strategic decisions. The history of results will be archived to provide input for an evaluation of the trend over time.

²¹ IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics: Conf. Series 898 (2017) 092056 doi :10.1088/1742-6596/898/9/092056